

Development of Sign Language Converter

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Abstract—This paper presents the development of a wearable glove that converts sign languages based on hand gesture protocol to text and speech. Sign language, a human communication protocol of speech impaired people, can also leverage on the convergence of computers and communication technology to expand the use of the language and ensure more integration and inclusion of speech impaired people into the main stream of socio-economic life. Existing works majorly proffer solutions based on image processing, however, this work presents the integration of flex sensors, accelerometer, Bluetooth connectivity and an android application to achieve smart glove prototype which basically converts hand gestures to speech and text in order to promote seamless sign language representation and translation. The device was tested and representation of 5 separate phrases was achieved. Hence, it proved to be a concept that can be realized and improved with increased build complexity.

Keywords—*sign language, hand gestures, flex sensors, embedded systems, assisted technologies.*

I. INTRODUCTION

According to the World Health Organization, over 5% of the world's population or 430 million people require rehabilitation to address their disabling hearing loss (432 million adults and 34 million children) [1]. It is estimated that by 2050, over 700 million people or one in every ten people will have disabling hearing loss. Furthermore, over 8.5 million Nigerians live with hearing loss [2]. Socio-economic activities require verbal communication hence, there is a need to standardize and integrate sign language which uses both hand gestures and facial expressions to communicate. Each country generally has its own, native sign language, and some have more than one. According to SignSolutions, there are more than 300 sign languages used around the world and these vary from nation to nation [3]. As there are many sign languages, it is quite challenging for non-sign language natives to understand, as the knowledge of sign language is limited to a fewer number of people.

On the other hand, advancement in computers and computing technologies has expanded the range of automated consumer products used to complete daily tasks and solve minor and major problems. An example is the modern-day smartphone, which has a very wide range of uses. The use of these technologies today cannot be overstated, as it provides an avenue for solving problems. The use of embedded systems to solve specific problems is common nowadays, and for those with a keen eye for problem solving with technology can take advantage of the use of embedded systems to solve problems.

Hence, there is an opportunity to develop a sign language recognition system to facilitate easier, accurate and flexible means of communication between speech impaired and unimpaired people. The development of a device to convert hand gestures to voice and text is required to address this problem while promoting inclusiveness of sign language natives.

II. RELATED WORKS

Recent studies have explored various methods for monitoring hand gestures using sensor gloves.

A. Image processing based Method

A hand gesture recognition system uses digital image processing techniques based on modified SIFT (Scale-Invariant Feature Transform) algorithm [4]. This algorithm is characterized by high processing speed which can produce efficient recognition results. However, the inaccuracies due to poor light intensity and image quality are major challenges. Although image processing technique may be faster than sensor-based technique, it is prone to a lot of errors. An image processing system was developed with the help of SURF (Speed up Robust Features) algorithm [5]. Video camera record hand movements, and the input video is partitioned into frames, for each frame, a set of features are extracted. This system is similar to the works in [4] except that it makes use of SURF algorithm instead of SIFT. SURF is better than SIFT in rotation invariant, blur and wrap transform, while SIFT is better than SURF in different scale images [6]. SURF is 3

times faster than SIFT because of the use of integral image and box filter. However, they are both exposed to the same disadvantages. The two approaches struggle with poor light intensity, and therefore, a technique that works regardless of lighting condition is required.

B. Sensor based Method

Sensor-based technique comprising of flex sensors, tactile sensors and accelerometer to translate American Sign Language gestures to both text and auditory voice was developed in [7]. However, it was only able to translate thirteen signs into their respective alphabets namely letters 'A' 'B' 'C' 'D' 'F' 'I' 'L' 'O' 'M' 'N' 'T' 'S' 'W' and the tactile sensors were used to improve the accuracy of three letters M, N and T. The use of an inertial measuring unit instead of an accelerometer would allow for a wider range of results. Another system was developed utilising five flex-sensors, two pressure sensors, and a 3-axis inertial motion sensor to distinguish the characters in the American Sign Language alphabet. The first version achieved an accuracy of 65.7% without pressure sensors while the second achieved an accuracy of 98.2% with pressure sensors [8]. However, the use of accelerometer will improve the accuracy.

The use of a cloth glove with flex sensors, LCD display and Bluetooth module were reported in [9],–the flex sensor monitored the bending in the fingers while the data were sent to the Arduino Uno microcontroller, which determines the gesture being made. The result is displayed on the LCD screen and then transmitted to an android application through the Bluetooth module. The use of LCD display instead of a software solution is not portable for real-life communications and the work did not consider the use of accelerometer which would provide more accurate readings by measuring hand movements and position in 3-Dimensional space. A sign language to digital voice conversion device consists of a glove with flex sensors, ARM STM32 microcontroller, SD card module, speakers and a power supply unit [10]. The microcontroller used data values from the flex sensors to determine the gesture being made and proceeded to play the corresponding voice file stored in the SD card, through the speakers. The accuracy and range of this approach is limited due to the use of only one type of data collection sensor, while an accelerometer with the flex sensors could achieve a wider range of values.

A Sign-Glove system designed to recognize sign language, implemented the device combining a bend sensor and an inertial sensor node [11]. The bend sensor was used to recognize hand shape, while the inertial sensor node recognised the hand motion. All the connections were made on breadboard, with a computer monitor screen used to display the output. The experiment chose twenty sign language words that were essential for hearing-impaired people in critical situations. Word-by-word sign language translation was achieved. However, in its presented form, the system has low mobility, which makes it unsuitable for practical use.

C. Machine Learning Method

A sign language classification approach employed an accelerometer and resistive sensors that spanned the hand joints; and machine learning algorithm that classified the data [12]. A pre-trained long short-term memory (LSTM) neural network was used to classify 12 American sign language letters and word in real time. However, the scalability of

LSTM is an issue due to its unsaturated learning capacity. A wearable electronic glove designed with new multi-layer parallel LSTM-CNN (Para-LSTM-CNN) network was presented in [13]. The device weighed only 126g, and utilized inertial measurement units (IMUs) and flex sensors to capture hand motion signals. The system was able to capture 41-dimensions of hand motion signals and the signals were uploaded to computer via the Wi-Fi. The algorithm also employed parallel features extraction strategy where temporal and spatial features of the sensor signals were extracted through LSTM and CNN, respectively. The Para-LSTM-CNN could effectively improve the accuracy of sign language recognition by fusing spatial and temporal features synchronously. The system showed a high sign language recognition accuracy of 97.01% for 26 gestures.

A device that combined AI-integrated prediction system in conjunction with wearable glove data was developed in [14] with progression learning deep convolutional neural networks (PLD-CNNs) to break down sentences into words for better analysis. The memetic optimization algorithm enhanced network performance, while, addressing recognition issues and improving learning efficiency. It was implemented using MATLAB, the system showed high precision, recall, accuracy, and F1 scores in recognizing sign language movements, thus making it a valuable tool for understanding sign-based sentences. Sensor glove fitted with flex sensors was used in [15] to capture hand movements and gestures. The data from these sensors were fed through a custom-built machine learning model trained on a comprehensive sign language dataset. The device recorded a recognition rate of 90% across a diverse set of signs, although there were challenges with expanding gesture recognition and refining translation algorithms.

D. Material based Method

A material-based method implemented a design, using copper plate [16]. This glove was made using small metal strips that were fixed on the five fingers of the glove. A copper plate was fixed on the palm as ground. It is better to use a ground plate instead of individual metal strips because the contact area for ground will facilitate easier identification of finger position. The copper strips indicated a voltage level of logic 1 in rest position. But when in contact with the ground plate, the associated voltage will drain and this indicated a voltage level of logic 0, thus, necessary gestures were formed. However, only one method for hand movement detection was accommodated, thus only lower range of gestures could be represented.

Another wearable organohydrogen-based electronic skin was developed [17] with fast self-healing, strong adhesion, extraordinary anti-freezing and moisturizing properties for sign language recognition under complex environments. The e-skin was obtained by using an acrylic network as the main body, aluminum (III) and bayberry tannin as the crosslinking agent, water/ethylene glycol as the solvent system, and a polyvinyl alcohol network was used to optimise the network performance. Using this e-skin, a smart glove was built, which could carry out the large-scale data collection of common gestures and sign languages. With the help of the deep learning method, specific recognition and translation for various gestures and sign languages could be achieved. An accuracy of 93.5% was obtained. The uniqueness of this work is the development of the material used to build the smart glove.

From the foregoing, varying approaches and tools have been used to develop smart glove or system that reads sign language and converts to text or speech. Depending on the technology and quality of tools used, several issues such as poor lighting with the use of image-based recognition, use of inadequate components, accuracy of detection and small variety of sensors used for the hardware-based approach have been raised. Thus, this paper focuses on the development of a sensor-embedded glove that translates hand gestures to speech and text through a mobile application.

III. METHODOLOGY

The tools and technology used in this design include Atmega328p microprocessor, Bluetooth (Bluetooth Module), Flex sensors, Accelerometer, Power module, Resistors, and Text-to-speech software (Bluetooth terminal app). The flex sensor measures the bending of fingers according to gesture and outputs change in resistances corresponding to the amount of bending. The accelerometer sensor measures the linear movements of hand in X-axis and outputs different values of X corresponding to the movement in X-axis. The data from the sensors are then processed by the Arduino NANO, which involves conditional statements wrapped around the sensor outputs in order to match the resultant output with pre-stored values of different signs regarding the registered phrases. In this design, appropriate ranges are set for each phrase that can be recognized with single hand, based on the measured data obtained from repeated measurements. The HC-05 Bluetooth module is connected to Arduino NANO. Figures 1 and 2 show the hardware and software case block diagrams for the design. The processed data are then transmitted to the Bluetooth

Fig. 1 Hardware case block diagram

Fig. 2 Software case block diagram with custom-built android mobile application

module (transmitter) in string format. The Android mobile also has an inbuilt Bluetooth capability. These two Bluetooth

devices are then paired, and the string is transmitted to the Android application. The Android application receives data via Bluetooth in bytes format, and then converts into string (Figure 3) while the string is converted into voice using the text to speech custom-built application of Android mobile. The overall system operation flow depicted in Figure 4 is mounted over a normal glove for easy handling and accurate recognition of the hand gestures.

Fig. 3 Flowchart of wearable smart glove

A. Theoretical Background of the Circuit Design

The main principles behind the design of this system are change in resistance, acceleration due to gravity and real-time serial communication. The relevance of resistance is towards how the flex sensor works. The more the flex sensor is bent, the greater the resistance. The conductive ink printed on the sensor acts as resistor. When the sensor is straight, this resistance is about 25KΩ. When the sensor is bent, the conductive layer is stretched, resulting in reduced cross section, with a consequent increased resistance. At 90° angle, this resistance is about 100KΩ, when the sensor is straightened again, the resistance returns to its original value.

By measuring the resistance, one can determine how much the sensor is bent.

Fig. 4 Flowchart of android application operation

The easiest way to read the flex sensor is to connect it with a fixed value resistor (usually 47KΩ) to create a voltage divider as shown in Figure 5. To do this, one end of the sensor is connected to the power and the other to a pull-down resistor. Then the point between the fixed value pull-down resistor and the flex sensor is connected to the ADC input of an Arduino. Thus, a variable voltage output is created, which can be read by Arduino's ADC input.

Fig. 5 A voltage divider scenario

The output measured is the voltage drop across the pull-down resistor (not across the flex sensor). The output of the voltage divider configuration is described by (1):

$$V_o = V_{cc} \frac{R}{R + R_{flex}} \quad (1)$$

In the shown configuration, the output voltage V_o decreases with increasing bend radius while V_{cc} and R remain constant, and R_{flex} increases. For example, with 5V supply and 47KΩ pull-down resistor, when the sensor is flat (0°), the resistance is relatively low (about 25KΩ). This results in the output voltage observed in (2)

$$V_o = V_{cc} \frac{47k\Omega}{47k\Omega + 25k\Omega} = 3.26v \quad (2)$$

When flexed all the way (90°), the resistance rises to 100KΩ. This results in the output voltage observed in (3)

$$V_o = 5V \frac{47k\Omega}{47k\Omega + 100k\Omega} = 1.59v \quad (3)$$

The relevance of acceleration due to gravity applies to the functionality of the ADXL 335 accelerometer. Acceleration due to gravity, denoted with the letter g , refers to any object moving under the sole influence of gravity at a value $9.8m/s^2$ downward. The accelerometer measures the static acceleration of gravity in tilt-sensing applications as well as dynamic acceleration resulting from motion, shock, or vibration. The real-time aspect is handled by the functionality of the Bluetooth module and the Android application. There is a synchronization of clocks between the HC-05 Bluetooth module and the Android application. The Bluetooth functionality in the Android application allows it to communicate seamlessly with the Bluetooth module due to synchronization of clocks.

B. Circuit Design

For Bend Sensing Module, the 5 flex sensors on the glove, are fitted for the 5 different fingers. The flex sensors change resistance depending on the amount of bend by the fingers. The Pin 1 of the flex sensor is connected to the 3.3v on the Arduino NANO, and then, the Pin 2 is connected to a 10 KΩ resistor, which acts as a voltage divider. The point between the pull-down resistor and the flex sensor is connected to the analogue Pin on the Arduino (Figure 6).

While in the Position Sensing module, the Accelerometer (ADXL 335), in this system is used as a tilt detector. It has an analogue output which varies from 1.5V to 3.5V. ADXL335 is a three-axis analogue accelerometer Integrated circuit (IC), which reads X, Y and Z axes acceleration as analogue voltages. By measuring the amount of acceleration due to gravity, an accelerometer

can figure out the angle it is tilted at, with respect to the earth. By sensing the amount of dynamic acceleration, the accelerometer can determine how fast and in what direction the movement is. The basic function of this module is to detect the tilting of the hand and send relevant data according to meaningful gestures, to the microcontroller which receives and saves the data.

Fig. 6 Bend sensing module

Figure 7 shows the interfacing of the Arduino NANO with the accelerometer to produce the position sensing module. In the Transmission Module (Figure 8), the Bluetooth module is responsible for transmitting output data to the mobile application, for enabling text to speech conversion and is made up of the HC-05 Bluetooth and the Arduino microcontroller.

Fig. 7 Position sensing module

Fig. 8 Transmission module

The microcontroller processes the phrase to be represented, transmits such data to the HC-05 and on to the android device which is connected to it through the Bluetooth. The complete schematic is as shown in Figure 9 based on the complete circuit diagram of Figure 10.

Fig. 9 Circuit diagram

Fig.10 Circuit schematic

The design of the Software Module consists of the Android application, designed using the Arduino integrated development environment (IDE).

C. Circuit Implementation

The circuit was implemented on a piece of perfboard, which was mounted on a neoprene glove. The components were soldered to the perfboard, and strings of thread were used to hold it onto the glove. The flex sensors were placed on the thumb, index finger and middle finger for testing. Conducting wires connect the flex sensors to the perfboard, on which 3 different voltage dividers are made to read values from the three different flex sensors. These values are sent as signals to the Arduino NANO microcontroller, which decodes the signals to their respective values. The accelerometer and HC-05 are connected directly to the microcontroller, and a USB cord used to power the Arduino, which in turn, powers the entire system. Figure 11 shows the device prototype.

Fig. 11. Prototype of smart glove

D. Custom Android Application Design

The Android application was designed and built with the MIT app inventor suite, and was tested with the use of an android phone and the Bluetooth module. The text and speech functionalities were implemented. MIT app inventor makes use of object-oriented visual scripting for programming the application as opposed to traditional programming. The development environment enabled switching between block and designer view, to ensure that changes being made while coding are seen in real-time. This also includes Bluetooth, text-to-speech and clock functionalities. Figure 12 shows the block view of the development environment.

Fig. 12 MIT App Inventor Block View

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In prototype testing, the readings are also visualized in graphical form in order to draw inferences. The results in Table 1 are obtained to determine that the flex sensors were working properly. Each result gesture was made up of separate resistance values for each finger. The tests were successful and each gesture was successfully represented.

TABLE I. TEST RESULTS FOR GESTURE DECODING

S/N	FLEX 1	FLEX 2	FLEX 3	FLEX 4	FLEX 5	RESULT
1	256	165	150	160	170	“ZERO”
2	150	256	130	120	120	“ONE”
3	180	256	256	130	130	“TWO”
4	256	256	256	130	130	“THREE”
5	141	256	256	256	256	“FOUR”

The graph in Figure 13 shows the difference in sensor values for each gesture made. On the Y-axis are the sensor values which are analogue value ranges 0 - 256. The more the bend, the lower the analogue value. The different coloured lines represent the gesture that is being made. For example, the phrase “FOUR” is depicted by flex sensor values of 141 for sensor 1, and 256 for the remaining sensors, which results in a mostly straight line. This implies that 4 of the 5 fingers are barely bent, and remain mostly straight, which means their analogue values are about 250-256. The thumb is the only finger bent, to a degree that produces the value 141. This is how gestures are represented with the use of flex sensors.

Figure 14 shows the bending angle for each flex sensor to produce the gesture “ZERO”. Flex 1 which is placed on

Fig. 13 Flex sensor responses for number gestures

the thumb has a bending angle of 0 degrees. This means the finger is straight, hence the angle. Flex 2, 3, 4 and 5 however, show bending angles of 58, 68, 50 and 55 degrees respectively. This shows that the fingers are bent and this makes sense because the physical representation of zero in sign language involves making a fist with the hand. The thumb stays straight while other fingers are bent. Values were forked from the accelerometer by creating new variables; nomx, nomy, and nomz which represent the original values of x, y and z in initial state, minus respective values which make nomx, nomy and nomz equal to 90 degrees at initial state

Fig. 14 Bending angle of each flex sensor for gesture “ZERO”

Figure 15 shows how this was achieved. This was done to make accelerometer range values easier to record. In the code segment, IF and ELSE statement were used to determine what will appear on the mobile application, based on the data values recorded. The variables involved are thumb, pointer, nomx and nomy, which change values when bending fingers and moving the hand in three-dimensional space.

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nomx = x-265;
nomy = y-253;
nomz = z-323;
    
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Fig.15 Forking out “nom” accelerometer values

Five phrases were recorded with stylized sign language representation, with pictorial representation are as shown in Figures 16-20. As seen in the examples, a range of values is

used for each finger. This is because human hands shake and move often, so a range of values is more adequate to represent gestures in the case of minor offsets. Ideally, having all backup units of fragile components like the flex sensor is important, due to the fact that they are used frequently in testing phases, and also, the fact that their pins are very tiny, thus have to be soldered with care.

Fig. 16 Gesture for “look forward”

“LOOK FORWARD” (thumb > 175) && (thumb < 200) && (pointer > 210) && (pointer < 235) && (nomx > 145) && (nomx < 160) && (nomy > 75) && (nomy < 95)

Fig. 17 Gesture for “look up”

“LOOK UP” (thumb > 175) && (thumb < 200) && (pointer > 210) && (pointer < 230) && (nomx > 70) && (nomx < 85) && (nomy > 20) && (nomy < 35)

Fig. 18 Gesture for “look down”

“LOOK DOWN” (thumb > 175) && (thumb < 200) && (pointer > 210) && (pointer < 235) && (nomx > 85) && (nomx < 100) && (nomy > 160) && (nomy < 175)

Fig. 19 Gesture for “Okay”

“OKAY” (thumb > 160) && (thumb < 195) && (pointer > 160) && (pointer < 180) && (nomx > 105) && (nomx < 125) && (nomy > 28) && (nomy < 43)

Fig. 20 Gesture for “Call me”

“CALL ME” (thumb > 230) && (thumb < 250) && (pointer > 150) && (pointer < 180) && (nomx > 145) && (nomx < 160) && (nomy > 80) && (nomy < 95)

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper presented a hardware-based approach and there are several other methods like image processing and machine learning that could be used. However, the hardware-based approach could further benefit from the following. Firstly, an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) with both a gyroscope and an accelerometer on the same device, may provide better accuracy and a wider possible range of readings and gesture representations. Furthermore, using 4.5-inch flex sensors as opposed to the 2.2-inch could overcome some difficulties in component connection, as the shorter length invariably caused damages to the flex sensors.

VI. CONCLUSION

Embedded systems have been the standard when it comes to providing specific technological solutions. There are several ways to achieve this while this paper proffered the use of sensors and a microcontroller to solve the presented problem. The prototype presented in this paper converts hand gestures of sign language to speech and text, and 5 separate

phrases were successfully represented and transformed to speech and text through the mobile application.

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